

BEST SOCIAL MEDIA PLATFORMS FOR REGISTERED ORGANIZATIONS ON CAMPUS

by

Nicole Lopez

ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6517-4605

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6654432

A Project Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the
Requirements to Graduate with University Honors

The University Honors Program
California State University, Fullerton
May 2022

Approved by:

Dr. Shelly Arsneault, Department of Humanities and Social Science

Dr. Yuying Tsong, Director University Honors Program

Date:

13 May 2022

5/31/2022

ABSTRACT

In recent years, social media usage has become a subconscious routine for most people. Not only is social media accessible in the United States but worldwide. Although social media has often been used as a source of entertainment, many institutions and organizations have begun to use social media as a platform for education. This was particularly evident during the COVID 19 pandemic when universities and organizations adopted virtual learning. Shifting from in-person to online has been a continuous struggle in participation and online engagement. Although there are recent studies on how social media is used for teaching, not much is known on how social media can be used to engage students in political participation. In this study, we want to see how a student organization can use social media as a platform for civic engagement. As the president of my registered organization, Planned Parenthood Generation Action, I wanted to know if social media can help promote student participation and help retain club members during a pandemic. This study explores which social media platforms from Titan Link, Instagram, and Discord engage members, advocates, and volunteers to attend virtual meetings and in-person events. By identifying which social platform is popular in staying informed and politically active, Planned Parenthood Generation Action will be able to build relationships to help promote more awareness of reproductive rights.

KEYWORDS: Social Media, Advocacy, College Campus, Online Engagement, Reproductive Rights, Planned Parenthood, COVID 19

INTRODUCTION

Planned Parenthood Generation Action (PPGEN) is a newly registered organization at California State University Fullerton (CSUF). It was originally created by Planned Parenthood Public Affairs in order to create change by building a network of young activists who educate individuals about how reproductive health is connected to immigration, civil rights, environment and identity politics (Parenthood, n.d). Due to this, Planned Parenthood Generation Action was created to advocate for Planned Parenthood health centers in order to provide every individual no matter race, gender, income, ability etc with access to health care services which includes abortion access (Planned Parenthood, n.d.). In order to support this movement, PPGEN at CSUF was formed so that young activists on college campuses can help mobilize advocates to raise public awareness about reproductive rights. It is an organization created to help educate college students or young adults about sexual health and create a network where young activists can come together to fight for reproductive access for everyone. Since Planned Parenthood Generation Action was officially created in March 2020 through student life and leadership at CSUF, one month before the global pandemic, PPGEN has to switch from in-person to virtual meetings. Trying to engage and retain members has been a challenge as a new club because COVID 19 limited our exposure on campus. Since social media is a marketing tool for many on-campus clubs, three different social media platforms (Titan Link, Discord, Instagram) will be studied to determine which forum best engages PPGEN members and encourages them to attend events and meetings for the club to meet our organizational goal in promoting access to reproductive rights through advocacy.

SCOPE OF STUDY

The scope of the study has been limited to three different social media marketing platforms. This includes Titan Link, Discord, and the club's Instagram account. This study has been limited to California State University Fullerton campus because the club is a campus-registered organization. Participants that will be in the study will be active CSUF students who have decided to become members in Planned Parenthood Generation Action.

OBJECTIVE OF STUDY

- A) To determine which social media platforms are used the most among college students.
- B) To study which platforms should be utilized more for club engagement.
- C) To determine which factors contributed to whether or not someone will attend a meeting.
- D) To utilize the information gathered to spread awareness on reproductive rights through social media.
- E) To identify common barriers as to why there is disengagement among college students.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Social Media is an important source of information

Social media is like a book with endless information. It is a vast network that provides a platform for sharing ideas, thoughts, documents, and resources. It provides a quick form of communication through the internet that can be accessed through phones, computers, laptops, and tablets. Examples of social media include Twitter, Instagram, Facebook, Snapchat, Titan Link, Discord and more. In recent years social media has become very popular because 83% of the young adults in America use social media (Velasquez, & LaRosa, 2014). Social media has been an essential source of information because it provides access online (Halpin et al., 2020;

Anderson et al., 2018). For instance, a social media platform like Twitter can have links attached to their tweets with people can click on the links to access further information about a topic (Bowen et al., n.d). Social media has been often used as a resource for political information and in recent years, the demand for this information has increased. For example, individuals have stated that they use social media to see where protests are occurring in their area, to provide support to a current movement by sharing information, to post an image associated with the protest, or to use hashtags to trend current political affairs (Anderson et al., 2018). Not only has social media been able to provide information to stakeholders but it has also helped promote awareness for many organizations.

Social Media can help promote awareness to your organization

As mentioned above, social media has been a marketing tool for various organizations to promote awareness for their products, content, brands, or trends. For example, Instagram, which is the second most popular social media platform, is used by many businesses to promote their brand through User-Generated Content, which can be in the form of a hashtag (Decker, n.d.). Since social media is where many individuals get their news, organizations use this information to share and post information about themselves. This can be seen through the volunteer organizations like Soroptimist because they would post about their organizational accomplishments, the hard work that each member has done, and promote activities that they planned to have (Soroptimist, n.d.). By providing information about an organization online, one can spread this information through social media to generate more awareness of an organization and its goals.

Social Media helps build relationships

Social media has been used to spread information, but it also helps connect people from around the world and build relationships (Heil, 2022). Through social media, communities come together and interact by commenting, sharing, liking, and posting information (Smith & Derville Gallicano, 2015). When it comes to organizations, they are trying to build a relationship with their stakeholders because having a positive relationship with the audience can help attract more attention to the organization's goals (Bowen et al., n.d.; Hou & Lampe, 2015; Smith & Derville Gallicano, 2015). Through the engagement of liking, commenting, sharing, one's involvement on social media helps connect individuals with others who share a common interest. Through this common interest, many build relationships and connections with others who are passionate about the same topic as themselves which can contribute to organizing protests or events for an important cause.

Social Media is creating more involvement from students

Social media can be accessed through apps and browsers that a person has on their phones, laptops, or computers. In recent years, the use of technology has increased, and according to Smith and Derville Gallicano (2015), college students before the age of 30 are more active on social media than others. When engaging in social media, the author stated that the individuals felt engaged when they interacted with the content and with the individuals through social media. (Smith & Derville Gallicano, 2015). Through social media, many users can stay connected and informed about the most up-to-date events and information. In the study by Smith and Derville Gallicano (2015), many college students were able to identify how being engaged with social media educated them by providing event information, fund-raisers that were occurring, active campaigns, or volunteer opportunities for an organization (Hou & Lampe, 2015). Overall, this

study demonstrated how social media attracted many college students and engaged them in learning about a topic since it was shared through social media.

Furthermore, Ternes (2013) emphasizes how social media is used the most when you have technology accessible to you. He states how the more a student uses social media, the more likely they will be involved in a student campus activity (Ternes, 2013). It focuses on the idea that social media is a form of communication. It's essential to use social media to keep students informed and engaged in activities on campus. Social media can offer a wide range of benefits like engaging a wide range of audiences, having immediate feedback, or even providing critical information to students about resources or events occurring on a college campus (Ternes, 2013). The research lets the reader know how social media has various features that can help attract and interact with students to campus life. For instance, on Discord, the channels are features that can be utilized to keep your website organized so club members can navigate the club easier (Chang, 2021). Social media like Instagram also has features like brand aesthetics that can be bold, stylish, colorful that can make an organization or club more recognizable to the millennial eye (Decker, 2006). Clubs and organizations can also utilize features like buying ads on Instagram that can boost and promote more interaction online (Decker, n.d.; Heil, 2022). Overall, there are various features, like those mentioned above, that can help promote more interaction with organizations and clubs among college students.

Barriers that prevent or motivate students from getting involved on campus

One form of getting involved in campus life is joining a club or an activity when entering college. According to Montelongo (2002), participation in club activities has been limited by a student's amount of time in college. Since a student is not on a college campus for an extended period, they miss the opportunities to create and interact with other students and organizations on

campus (Montelongo, 2002). Why might a student not be spending time on campus, you may ask? According to Hegedus and Knight (n.d.), factors that have prevented student participation were student's availability, schoolwork, employment, the organizations offered were not professional, they viewed no benefit to joining the club, or having family priorities. When asked what prevented them from participating in student activities, time management has been restated in multiple students' responses (Nunes Achar Fujii et al., 2021). This is also supported by Boyd's (2013) research because he states how a student's career and family priorities keep students away from attending any classrooms on campus. This results in students choosing to pick online classes since they won't have to commute to school, and online courses work better with their scheduling (Boyd, 2013). It's essential to acknowledge how environmental factors in a student's life play a significant role in determining whether a student will be involved on campus.

Slacktivism

Many organizations have used social media to promote their organizational goals. This has often been a re-post that an organization is trying to promote online (White & Pelozo, 2014; Seay, 2014; Lodewijckx, 2020). One main challenge that many nonprofit organizations or organizations, in general, have seen within advocates is how many want to make a minimal amount of effort to support a cause; this is also known as slacktivism (Kristofferson et al., 2014; Seay, 2014; Lodewijckx, 2020). Although re-posting and promoting issues online promotes awareness, advocates want to ensure that their advocacy efforts don't require extended participation, like dedicating a whole day to advocating for a political issue (Seay, 2014). One main problem with slacktivism has been that there is no way to measure its effectiveness in making a change in society (Lodewijckx, 2020; Kristofferson et al., 2014). This is important. Although using social media effectively promotes awareness, it does not guarantee that policy

changes occur because people still need to show up and vote.

Disengagement

With the recent pandemic, returning to school in person has been a difficult process for engagement. According to McMurtie (2022), many professors have seen a very concerning level of disconnection among students. Many students want to be engaged, but they still feel very disconnected from the university even though they have returned on campus (McMurtie, 2022; Sunil, 2021). To encourage student participation, introducing serious conversations about controversial topics seems to encourage students to participate more (McMurtie, 2022). Universities are trying to create a sense of normalcy so that students can begin to be more engaged with the university; however, due to covid, it has been a struggle that many professors have been facing (McMurtie, 2022; Sunil, 2021).

METHODS

IRB Approval

The Institutional Review Board (IRB) is a committee that protects the rights of all human subjects research that is conducted at CSUF. There were five steps that I had to take to proceed with my research. The first was to ask myself if my survey needed IRB approval. Since I was working with human subjects, I did need to get my project approved by the IRB which moved me to my second step, which was to complete the Collaborative Institutional Training Initiative (CITI) through Cayuse IRB. Once my training was finished, I needed to gather all my documents: a Cayuse IRB account, CITI training certificate, my project description, and Supplemental documents (Informed Consent forms, Questionnaires/Surveys and Debriefing documents). Once my documents were gathered, I was able to submit my protocols through the

IRB CSUF website. Although I submitted my documentation, I still needed approval from the IRB, which consisted of providing more clarification about my research project. This IRB process lasted about one month, almost two, before I was able to begin my project in October 2021.

Design

The design of the study was qualitative and observational research design. This is because a google form survey was created to capture each participant's data. It was observational because I would visually see how many people showed up to the club events promoted through social media. Five questions were designed for the student activist to fill out that would reflect the best social media platforms Planned Parenthood Generation Action should use and barriers that would prevent student participation. Engagement in this study was when a student showed up to an online event or a zoom event promoted through Titan Link, Instagram, and Discord. There were eight events; four were in person at the titan walk, and four were over zoom that the students could have participated in. The students had to stay for a minimum of 10 minutes to be considered active participants in the study.

Consistent Variables

The variables that remained the same during the duration of the project were:

1. Time
2. Location
3. Incentives
4. Research Questions

5. Dates
6. Participants
7. Social Media Sites
8. Times events were posted

The time of the study remained consistent from 2-3 pm. The events' location in person was at the California State University Campus located at the Titan walk, whereas the online sites were executed through zoom. For this project, two 15-dollar incentives were given at an opportunity drawing at the end of the month to those who showed up to events posted on social media. The five research questions were presented at each event for the student participants to fill out. The dates stayed consistent throughout the experiment because it was every other Tuesday from the months of October, November, February, and March. The sample of the study were students enrolled in CSUF for Fall 2021 and Spring 2022 semester. More specifically, the students who actively participated in Planned Parenthood Generation Action. The social media sites used to promote events were Instagram, Titan Link, and Discord. Titanlink was promoting the events the entire semester as well as directing student's interested in PPGEN to the Instagram page and Discord groupchat that PPGEN created. For Instagram and Discord, the events were consistently posted one week before the event, one day before the event, and the day of the event. All these variables remained constant throughout the duration of the experiment to prevent confusion with the results.

Consent Forms

Once a student was connected to our advertising platforms like mentioned above, I would advertise the event one week before, one day before, and the day of the event through Discord

and Instagram to remind the members about events they could participate in. For those members who showed up at the events, before given a survey, they were asked to read and sign a consent form which included the purpose of the study, what was being asked of the member, if any benefits were included, if the information provided were to be kept anonymous, contact information, the participant's rights and the signature of the participants and investigator.

Survey

Once the consent form was signed, each participant was asked to take an exit survey to provide me feedback on which social media platform is the most effective in attracting individuals to participate in virtual meetings and social events. The first part of the survey asks how the individuals heard about the event and which platform Planned Parenthood Generation Action needs to start utilizing to attract more members to meetings and events. The second part of the survey seeks to understand why individuals may not show up to events. The survey was conducted online through a google survey; however, if we did a social event in person, students were asked to fill out a paper survey which was later converted into a google survey. The survey duration was 1-3 minutes, depending on how long the person took to log into the google forms. Refer to Figure 1.1 and Figure 1.2 in the appendix for visual presentation.

RESULTS

The results demonstrated that social media did play a factor in where the students received their information on Planned Parenthood Generation Action Events. Three out of the five questions proved to be the most significant in this study based on the asked questions. The questions that we will be focusing on are:

1. Where did you hear about this event from?

2. What social media should we use to advertise future events?
3. If you were not to come to the event, what would be the most likely outcome?

Below are the graphs that show the results:

Figure 2.1

Figure 2.1 tells us that Instagram and Discord were utilized the most to obtain information about club events.

Figure 2.2

Figure 2.2 tells us that Instagram and Discord are the most preferred social media platforms among CSUF Planned Parenthood Generation Action members.

Figure 2.3

Figure 2.3 tells us that among the PPGEN members, the most likely reason they did not show up to events promoted through Titan Link, Instagram, and Discord was that the participants had other school priorities.

LIMITATIONS:

There were three main limitations that I was able to identify during the duration of my research project: Representation, Covid-19, and Time.

Representation

Representation was a significant factor when it came to obtaining my data. As a new club at CSUF, Planned Parenthood Generation Action struggled to recruit and retain new members. This can be seen through the number of participants in the study. Of 37 people who were signed up to be informed on our Discord chat, only 5 participants were able to show up to events promoted through social media and take the surveys during the research duration. Having only five individuals take the survey is not representative of the whole population at the CSUF campus.

COVID-19

Covid-19 was a limitation because it limited our exposure on campus. Covid-19 forced all student activity online instead of in person. Due to this, if people were not searching for an

advocacy club, they would not be able to find Planned Parenthood Generation Action. Covid-19 was also a limitation because it forced me to restart my whole research project. I originally had a different project that I was going to conduct on-campus, but because everything switched online, I could not continue with my original research. This resulted in Covid-19 influencing a lack of disengagement within the PPGEN club.

Time

Lastly, time was a limitation because the research project was started late. It resulted in me getting less time to extend my research. Four months is not enough time to obtain data on which social media platform is preferred among college students. To add, I had a schedule conflict with work and school, which limited my time spent on the project. I would have loved to extend my project to more than the four months of October, November, February, and March.

CONCLUSION

This study provides an understanding of how social media can promote engagement. From the survey results, I was able to identify how Instagram and Discord were utilized for updates on events. As the president of Planned Parenthood Generation Action, the results told me that more college students prefer to get their information from Instagram. The survey also highlighted how the main barrier why people don't show up to events is because PPGEN members have other school priorities that they need to focus on. By knowing which platform is preferred, the study tells me to start utilizing this Instagram to promote future events.

One lesson learned throughout the study is that people show support and advocate, but it is minimal; slacktivism. During the duration of my study, 73 petitions were signed within the four

days that Planned Parenthood Generation Action Members participated in events. This means that about 15-20 signatures were signed per day when the events of the experiment were in person. This is significant because it shows that there are people who want to support advocacy clubs on campus however they refuse to participate.

The disengagement among students has been a struggle for Planned Parenthood Generation Action. Even though incentives were being promoted, students still chose not to participate. Students were consistently reminded of the events before they took place. Even with the reminders through social media, disengagement with student life was still occurring.

Overall, future research still needs to be done to see which social media platforms are preferred among college students. This is because the research needs to be representative of the whole population. It needs to include other clubs and other college campuses to be representative. The duration of the study needs to be longer to get the data required to show the effectiveness of social media usage in promoting participation.

APPENDIX A

Figure 1.1

Exit Ticket

Before you leave the meeting today, answer the following questions.

[Switch account](#)

*** Required**

Name *

Your answer _____

Where did you hear about this event from? *

Instagram

Titanlink

Discord

From an event

Other: _____

Which social media should we use to advertise future events? *

Instagram

Titanlink

Discord

Other: _____

Figure 1.2

We advertise one week before, one day before, and the day of the event. Are we advertising

Too often

Just right

Not enough

Will you be back again? *

Yes

Probably

Probably Not

No

If you were to not come to the events, what would be the most likely reason? *

Family Priorities

Job

Event didn't interest me

Too tired/ Need a break

School Priorities

Other: _____

Submit Clear form

APPENDIX B

Figure 2.4

Figure 2.5

References

- Anderson, M., Toor, S., Olmstead, K., Rainie, L., & Smith, A. (2018, July 11). *Activism in the Social Media Age*. Pew Research Center.
<https://www.pewresearch.org/internet/2018/07/11/public-attitudes-toward-political-engagement-on-social-media/>
- Bowen, G. A., Gordon, N. S., & Chojnacki, M. K. (n.d.). *Advocacy Through Social Media: Exploring Student Engagement in Addressing Social Issues*. ERIC.
<https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1156183.pdf>
- Boyd, D. (2013, January 30). *The Characteristics of Successful Online Students*. Onlinelibrary.
<https://onlinelibrary-wiley-com.lib-proxy.fullerton.edu/doi/10.1002/nha3.10184>
- Chang, F. (2021, September 9). *Ten Tips to Help Your College Club Bloom on Discord*. Discord.
<https://discord.com/blog/ten-tips-to-help-your-college-club-bloom-on-discord>
- Decker, A. (n.d.). *Instagram Marketing: The Ultimate Guide*. HubSpot.
https://www.hubspot.com/instagram-marketing?__hstc=76279882.3e0a5a1b751c3aa420ef9892abf0b287.1646784404169.1646784404169.1646784404169.1&__hssc=76279882.2.1646784404169&__hsfp=2619436724
- Halpin, D. R., Fraussen, B., & Ackland, R. (2020, December 21). *Which Audiences Engage With Advocacy Groups on Twitter? Explaining the Online Engagement of Elite, Peer, and Mass Audiences With Advocacy Groups*. sagepub.
<https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/full/10.1177/0899764020979818>
- Hegedus, C. M., & Knight, J. (n.d.). *Student Participation in Collegiate Organizations – Expanding the Boundaries*. Association of Leadership Educators.
<https://www.leadershipeducators.org/Resources/Documents/Conferences/Lexington/Hegedus.pdf>
- Heil, E. (2022, March 30). *Mastering Social Media for Clubs: Go Beyond Likes and Shares*. StoryTeller Media. <https://www.storytellermn.com/ccm/social-media-for-clubs>

Hou, Y., & Lampe, C. (2015, May). *Social Media Effectiveness for Public Engagement: Example of Small Nonprofits*. researchgate.

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/276919385_Social_Media_Effectiveness_for_Public_Engagement_Example_of_Small_Nonprofits

Kristofferson, K., White, K., & Peloza, J. (2014, April). *The Nature of Slacktivism: How the Social Observability of an Initial Act of Token Support Affects Subsequent Prosocial Action*.

researchgate.

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/271799132_The_Nature_of_Slacktivism_How_the_Social_Observability_of_an_Initial_Act_of-Token_Support_Affects_Subsequent_Prosocial_Action

Lodewijckx, I. (2020, May 20). *'Slacktivism': Legitimate Action or Just Lazy Liking?* CitizenLab.

<https://www.citizenlab.co/blog/civic-engagement/slacktivism/>

McMurtrie, B. (2022, April 5). *A 'Stunning' Level of Student Disconnection*. The Chronicle of Higher Education. <https://www.chronicle.com/article/a-stunning-level-of-student-disconnection>

Montelongo, R. (2002). *Student Participation in College Student Organizations: A Review of Literature* | *Journal of the Student Personnel Association at Indiana University*. Open Access.

<https://scholarworks.iu.edu/journals/index.php/jiuspa/article/view/4617>

Nunes Achar Fujii, R., Kobayasi, R., Enns, S. C., & Tempski, P. Z. (2021, March 11). *Student Prole: Motivations, Contributions and Barriers to Engage in Extracurricular Activities*. researchsquare.

https://assets.researchsquare.com/files/rs-267525/v1_covered.pdf?c=1631858084

Planned Parenthood. (n.d.). *About Planned Parenthood Generation Action*. Planned Parenthood Action Fund.

<https://www.plannedparenthoodaction.org/communities/planned-parenthood-generation-action/about-planned-parenthood-generation-action>

Seay, L. (2014, March 12). *Does slacktivism work?* washingtonpost.

https://www.washingtonpost.com/news/monkey-cage/wp/2014/03/12/does-slacktivism-work/?pwap_token=eyJ0eXAiOiJKV1QiLCJhbGciOiJIUzI1NiJ9.eyJzdWJpZCI6IjY2MDQ3NjkiLCJyZW

Fzb24iOiJnaWZ0IiwibmJmIjoxNjQ5MTI3MTU1LCJpc3MiOiJzdWJzY3JpcHRpb25zIiwilZlXhw
IjoxNjUwMzM2NzU1LC

Smith, B. G., & Derville Gallicano, T. (2015, July 7). *Terms of engagement: Analyzing public engagement with organizations through social media*. sciencedirect.

<https://reader.elsevier.com/reader/sd/pii/S0747563215004756?token=8430CB9913CAB5DC80C4745AD99C595C1510DA35DE621A6EFDF5BFF9CFECB0CC6C3AC1C29EB8CE16570E6A64B5AAC744&originRegion=us-east-1&originCreation=20220513022735>

Soroptimist. (n.d.). *Social Media Guide for Clubs and Regions*. imgix.

<https://soroptimist.imgix.net/05-for-members/recognition-and-branding-tools/social-media-materials/social-media-policy-guidelines-clubs.pdf>

Sunil, B. (2021, April 27). *UNL students face a loss of community connection during COVID-19*. Daily Nebraskan.

https://www.dailynebraskan.com/magazine/unl-students-face-a-loss-of-community-connection-during-covid-19/article_cb4ec3ac-a6b9-11eb-aafe-5f57e846dbfd.html

TERNES, J. A. (2013). *USING SOCIAL MEDIA TO ENGAGE STUDENTS IN CAMPUS LIFE* by JACOB A. TERNES BSE, Emporia State University, 2009 A REPORT submitte. CiteSeerX.

<https://krex.k-state.edu/dspace/bitstream/handle/2097/15596/JacobTernes2013.pdf?sequence=5>

Velasquez, A., & LaRose, R. (2014, January 7). *Youth collective activism through social media: The role of collective efficacy* - Alcides Velasquez, Robert LaRose, 2015. SAGE Journals.

<https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/abs/10.1177/1461444813518391>